

University of Medicine, Mandalay

Small Group Facilitative Teaching-Learning Practice, Feedback Report of Third M.B.B.S & Final Part I Student Classes (7/2016), for Jul-Dec 2016

Reported by Dr. Htain Lin Aung
Demonstrator
Department of Pathology
University of Medicine, Mandalay

30th December 2016

TO __ PROFESSOR & HEAD __ PROF: DR. SAN SAN HLAING
__ RECTOR __ PROF: DR. KHIN MAUNG LWIN
CC __ PRORECTOR __ PROF: DR. AYE AYE CHIT

Contents:

1. General	5
2. Objectives	5
3. Teaching-Learning Design & Methods used	6
4. Teaching-Learning Aids	8
5. Small Group Discussion (SGD) Feedback form	9
6. Final Part I Report	10
6.1. Time Table of Teaching-Learning Activity and its feedback collection for Final Part I	10
6.2. Teaching Learning Practice Overall narrative Report	10
6.3. SGD Feedback Chart (Final Part I – Overall)	11
6.4. SGD Mood Meter Overall	11
6.a. SGD FP1 Roll No (71-140) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used	12
6.b. SGD FP1 Roll No (141 -190) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used	13
6.c. SGD FP1 Roll No (1-70) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used	14
6.d. SGD FP1 Roll No (441-490) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used	15
6.e. SGD FP1 Roll No (301-375) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used	16
6.f. SGD FP1 Roll No (301-375) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used	17
7. Third M.B.B.S Report	18
7.1. Time Table of Teaching-Learning Activity and its feedback collection for Third M.B, B.S	18
7.2. Teaching Learning Practice Overall narrative Report	18
7.3. SGD Feedback Chart (Third M.B, B.S-Overall)	19
7.4. SGD Mood Meter Overall	19
7.a. SGD Third MB Roll No (63-105) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used ..	20
7.b. SGD Third MB Roll No (167-226) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used ..	21
7.c. SGD Third MB Roll No (106-166) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used ..	22
7.d. SGD Third MB Roll No (1-62) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used	23
7.e. SGD Third MB Roll No (376-419) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used ..	24
7.f. SGD Third MB Roll No (271-314) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used ..	25
7.g. SGD Third MB Roll No (227-270) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used ..	26
8. Comparison of Feedback Chart Between FP1 & Third MB Students during Jul-Dec 2016	27
9. Lesson Learnt & Challenges & solving them	28
10. Problem Tree Drawing for “Dull & Unhappy Teaching Unit” (Cause → Problem → Effect)	28

11. Constructed FB & Comprehensive Actions to be carried out for “Dull & Unhappy Teaching Unit” ...	29
12. Photo Reporting	31

1. General

Since I have entered into the government sector as a demonstrator in the pathology department of university of Medicine, Mandalay last March, I am very interested to conduct the teaching-learning practice in facilitative teaching style instead of traditional style in small group discussion (SGD), which we call “tutorial class”. Although we, newly recruited staff, started to work last March, we actually dialed with the teaching activities on July when the school was open.

The demonstrators in Pathology Department have to dial the teaching practice not only for Third M.B, B.S tutorial classes but also for Final Part I classes while they have to teach the Morbid Practical session only for the assigned academic year. This report is exclusively for the small group discussion (Tutorials) for third M.B, B.S and final Part I within the period of July-December 2016.

Although there has to be a total of 16 SGD classes (described in No.6.1 & 7.1) for both academic years (third MB & FP I) to meet with all the students counting 8 sessions for each, I could facilitate only **13 SGD classes** because there has to teach only 6 sessions for FP I & 7 sessions for Third MB students during reporting period (Jul-Dec). After each and every SGD, I gathered the feedback for my **facilitative teaching learning style** (described in No.4) by **SGD feedback form** (described in No.4). **The summary and the details** of this report are described in No.6 & No.7.

Most of all, there was the time to facilitate “**Problem tree of Dull & Unhappy Teaching Unit**” with the final part I students (376-430) when I had a chance to get a couple sessions for the same class by binding the academic topic into one session. This really was fantastic and **described in No. 10 & 11** together with their constructed feedback and it is recorted departmental ISO documentation in Pathology department.

2. Objectives

- a) **To maintain accountability for better teaching-learning practice as an education service provider** while producing competent doctors by effective medical educators
- b) **To use the happiness of the students as an indicator in enjoyable teaching-learning practice** while producing competent doctors by effective medical educators
- c) **To adopt the facilitative teaching styles as student-centered approach** while producing competent doctors by effective medical educators

3. Teaching Learning Design & Methods used

I had introduced with so many kinds of different teaching learning styles to conduct the SGD very productive and not to get bored in the class by student center approaches. Although all the SGD sessions that I conducted were not used the same methods because of the unlike condition of the students and space availability of the room & its table and chair arrangement, I did many in common.

The methods used in each different SGD session are described with its mood meter feedback later in this report. The following table shows the methods used and its descriptions.

Table 1. Teaching Methods used and its description

No.	Teaching Methods	Description	How it works
1.	Grouping	To count every students to 1,2,3,4 then they ought to gather Group 1,2,3,4 by their no.	To get gender balance, To Split their profound grouping style, To meet with new friendship
2.	Focus Group Discussion on the flip charts by giving different Brain Storming problems/Photos	For Same tutorial topic, each group will has to deal with different disease problems by open book discussion within the SGD	To get a focus discussion for a specific topic within the SGD group by better communication skill
3.	Group MCQ study by giving prize (Candy)	Open book study for printed MCQ for the specific topic among different SGD groups by giving prize for the group of highest score	To challenge their winning interest as well as their wanting to know the exact answer of the questions
4.	Old Questions Study	Let them browse some links (described in teaching aids topic) that created before the class concerning with old questions of the respective tutorial topic	To get a sense that they can use their phone and Internet within the SGD groups freely but not for social media application that is restricted dominantly.
5.	Gallery Shows	Some of the pathways, figures & Pneumonic of the Topic diseases are printed or drawn before the class and then to stick those papers on the walls	Not to sit the students all the one-hour time. Let them move from one picture to another while facilitative teacher

		of the room like a picture gallery shows.	opens with them discussion about the pictures.
6.	Open Discussion by World-Cafè Method	With the music background opening, there will be four different Café tables (assumed) with four different groups owning four different disease problems. After each & every 10-15 mins, students has to move another Cafè Shop for different discussion topic while someone (assumed as Cafè Owner) within the group has to facilitate the other participants for filling missed information then he has to present to all the students in final discussion.	To get active participation and stress released discussion freely in SGD room.
7.	Presentation Session (2-5mins) for a problem topic)	One of the students within each group whom they prefer as their representative has to present the topic that they got, loudly, actively & precisely for only 2-5mins.	To get active participation and to make them believe that they can do self-study by themselves sometimes. To get well time management
8.	Final Discussion by facilitative teacher	Ask them what they want to know more about the topic discussion. & Get brief discuss “Should Know, Must know, Good to know facts” with the students.	To get Student center teaching-learning style in active ways.
9.	Teaching Learning Aids Sharing Session	Some of the MCQ/MSQ Questions links precisely created from old questions for the exact tutorial topic for their further study has been introduced.	To let them use the Internet for teaching-learning practice.
10.	EndEvaluation Feedback	Gather their feedbacks by the feedback form after letting them to fill for just one min.	To make a better teaching-learning practice in future To know their response

4. Teaching Aids

Apart from desk, tables and chairs, the followings were prepared for the productive teaching learning practice & to make students comfortable within the SGD room.

Table 2. Teaching Aids used

No.	Teaching-Learning Aids
1.	A0 Flip Chart
2.	Markers (Colorful)
3.	Sticky Notes
4.	Double Tapes
5.	Candy for prize sessions
6.	Colorful printed picture for Brain Storming
7.	Some Internet Links for Old Question Study MSQ/MCQ Old Questions Some Eg. For 3 rd M.B, B. S Students drhtain.com/dl/3mbsq/inflmhr.pdf drhtain.com/dl/3mbsq/cinjTEIS.pdf drhtain.com/dl/3mbcq/inflmk.pdf drhtain.com/dl/3mbcq/teidk.pdf drhtain.com/dl/3mbcq/trozooi.pdf Some Eg. For Final Part I Students drhtain.com/dl/fp1cq/bloodtk.pdf drhtain.com/dl/fp1cq/breastk.pdf drhtain.com/dl/fp1cq/haemolysisk.pdf drhtain.com/dl/fp1cq/myelok.pdf

5. Small Group Discussion (SGD) Feedback form

Date -
Class - Third M.B/ Final Part 1

Small Group Discussion (SGD) End Evaluation/ Feedback form

Please rate the following aspects of the whole SGD.

သင်ခန်းစာ ဆွေးနွေးပိုင်း နှင့်ပတ်သတ် ပြီးအောက်ပါအ မြင်များကို ကျေးဇူးပြု၍ သတ်မှတ်ပေးပါ။

Topic Discussion:	Poor ညံ့		Average သင့်		Excellent အကောင်းဆုံး
Room: PR1, PR2, PR3, A1, A4	1	2	3	4	5
Small Group Discussion is relevant to my needs. သင်ခန်းစာဆွေးနွေးပိုင်းသည်ကျွန်ုပ်၏ လိုအပ်ချက်နှင့် ကိုက်ညီမှုရှိပါသည်။					
Materials provided were helpful. သင်ထောက်ကူပစ္စည်းများသည် အထောက်အကူဖြစ်ပါသည်။					
Length of the SGD was sufficient. အချိန်လုံလောက်မှုရှိပါသည်။					
Questions were encouraged. မေးခွန်းမေးရန်အားပေးသည်။					
The facilitator was effective. ဦးဆောင်သူ(ဆရာ/မ) သည်ထိရောက်စွာ ဦးဆောင်ဆွေးနွေးနိုင်သည်။					
Content was well organized. အကြောင်းအရာများသည် စနစ်တကျ စီစဉ်ထားရှိပါသည်။					
SGD Methodology is effective. သင်ခန်းစာဆွေးနွေးပိုင်း နည်းစနစ်များသည်ထိရောက်မှုရှိပါသည်။					
Discussion Room is feeling comfortable. ဆွေးနွေးသည့် အခန်းသည် စိတ်သက်တောင့်သက်သာရရှိစေသည်။					

Other Comments:/ မှတ်ချက်:

Please tick on the Mood Meter
ကျေးဇူးပြု၍ စိတ်ပျော်ရွှင်မှု အခြေအနေပြဇယား တွင်အမှတ်ခြစ်ပေးပါ။

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class					
After the Class					

A Million Thanks for your participation. Wish you all students have a great day!

SGD feedback form continue:

Honestly, the above SGD feedback form is adopted and edited from the training feedback form. It is added the mood meter feedback below the paper **for the indicator of students' happiness** about the class. Every sector of the feedback form can be freely marked from **the lowest score to the highest (0-5) with the sense of 3 that is average**. The form can measure not just only about **the teachers' effectiveness** but also **teachers' management with the class within very limited one hour**. The student's feedback is used in my SGD room for the accountability of the education service we deliver. Combined and each feedback result of every tutorial class that I have delivered are reported as No.6 & No.7.

The PDF document of the SGD feedback form can be downloaded as

drhtain.com/dl/other/SGDevaluationform.pdf

6. Report for Final Part I

6.1. Time Table of Teaching-Learning Activity and its feedback collection for Final Part I

Although there were total 7 SGD sessions for Final Part I class in this reporting period (Jul-Dec/2016), I am now submitting the combined report remaining the SGD activity for Roll no 191-316. Since I have conducted the SGD sessions with the total actual attendance of **242** over 370 among total 490 students, I have met with **49.38% of the total final part I students** who gave me the constructed feedback in this period. The following table 1 shows in detail.

Table 3. Time Table of Teaching-Learning Activity and its feedback collection from Final Part I (Jul/Dec 2016)

Final Part 1	A1	PR1	PR2	PR3
FP1 Roll No. 1-242 Tutorial Session	RN- 1-70 (Total -70) 9.8.16/7:30-8:30AM Actual Attendance: 47	RN- 71-140 (Total-70) 21.7.16/3:30-4:30PM Actual Attendance: 46	RN - 141-190 (Total-50) 1.8.16/15.8.16/3:30-4:30PM Actual Attendance: 28	RN- 191-242
FP1 Roll No. 243-490 Tutorial Session	RN- 243-316	RN- 301-375 (Total-75) 2.11.2016/3:30-4:30PM Actual Attendance: 65	RN- 376-430 (Total-55) 23.11.2016/3:30-4:30PM Actual Attendance: 45	RN- 441-490 (Total-50) 27.9.16/ 7:30-8:30AM Actual Attendance: 11

6.2. Teaching-Learning Practice Overall narrative report

After committing a pilot teaching-learning practice during these 6 months, the following result was undertaken. **The lowest score** that they marked as 3.27 over 5 is about the **Teaching Aids** that I have used by own budget. It is so happy to agree with the feedback & real situations of the Teaching Aids used in practice nowadays. **The second lowest** score is **the Discussion room**, which is also need to be upgraded with standardized furniture and pleasant arrangement for discussion. **The third is length of SGD, which is ever given as just only one hour for a full chapter topic sometimes a couple chapters**. That ought to be in a more appropriate time for the better teaching learning style. Others sector is scored as above 3.5/5. Although the marking for the leading facilitative teacher is getting 4/5 exactly, the overall practice is scored as 3.6 in average. The following is the detailed data for the feedback.

6.3. SGD Feedback Chart (Final Part I - Overall)

6.4. SGD Mood Meter Chart (Final Part I – Overall)

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	19%	31%	37%	4%	10%
After the Class	43%	33%	13%	2%	9%

The above mood meter feedback from the total actual attendance of SGD class which was total **242 final part one students** shows 43% happy and 33% Ok. That represents productively that **over 75% of the total actual attendance felt great after the SGD classes.**

The data of feedback form, mood meter and the teaching methods used for each SGD class (6 in total FPI) are described as No. 6.a to 6.f in the following_

6.a. SGD FP1 Roll No (71-140) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

**SGD FP1 PR1 (21.7.2016/ 3:30-4:30PM 46/70 persons)
Topic Discuss - (Haemolytic Anaemia & Anaemia of S/D)
Mood Meter feedback**

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	16%	38%	33%	7%	9%
After the Class	24%	47%	20%	7%	4%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. MCQ open book study & Winning prize among the groups
3. Focus Group Discussion
4. Googling and internet browsing
5. End evaluation feedback collection

6.b. SGD FP1 Roll No (141 -190) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

SGD FP1 PR1 (1.8.2016/ 3:30-4:30PM 28/50 persons)
Topic Discuss - (WBC Disorder & Leukemoid Blood Picture)
Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	14%	25%	39%	11%	11%
After the Class	46%	39%	7%	0%	7%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. MCQ open book study & Winning prize among the groups
3. Brain Storming by problem Photo questions
 - (a. Toxic Neutrophil,
 - i. b. blood film of eosinophilia
 - ii. c. Felty’s Syndrome (neutropenia, hypersplenism, RA)
 - iii. d. Dohle’s body)
4. Focus Group Discussion
5. Googling and internet browsing
6. End evaluation feedback collection

6.c. SGD FP1 Roll No (1-70) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

SGD FP1 PR1 (9.8.2016/ 7:30-8:30AM 47/70 persons)
Topic Discuss - (Blood Groups & Blood Transfusion)
Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	13%	38%	40%	4%	4%
After the Class	68%	21%	9%	0%	2%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. MCQ open book study & Winning prize among the groups
3. Brain Storming by problem questions
 - (a. Is air embolism important in blood transfusion? Why do u think so?
 - b. How do you understand massive blood transfusion? Is it dangerous sometimes to the patients?
 - c. Are you sure that blood group "O" is universal donor? Why do/don't you think so?
 - d. Why does blood grouping and matching detect some previously known blood group A or B patient as wrong with correct samples?)
4. Focus Group Discussion
5. Presentation and sharing the discussion to other participants
6. Googling and Internet browsing. 7. End evaluation feedback collection

6.d. SGD FP1 Roll No (441-490) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

SGD FP1 PR1 (27.9.2016/ 7:30-8:30AM 11/50 persons)
Topic Discuss - (Fibrocystic disease & Tumors of Breast)
Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	9%	36%	45%	0%	0%
After the Class	36%	55%	0%	0%	0%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. Topic discussion other than the technical such as the Speech's of State Counselor on UN Meeting
3. MCQ open book study
4. Focus Group Discussion
5. File sharing by internet browsing
6. End evaluation feedback collection

(Note - One student out of eleven did not mark the mood feeling table although he commented, as he was sleepy so bad.)

6.e SGD FP1 Roll No (301-375) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

SGD FP1 PR1 (2.11.2016/ 3:30-4:30PM 65/75 persons)

Topic Discuss - (Diseases of Gallbladder)

Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	23%	25%	32%	3%	17%
After the Class	43%	25%	14%	3%	15%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. Open book study Group Discussion by World Cafe' Method
3. Group Discussion by World Cafe' Method with respective pictures
 - a. Etiology & Pathogenesis of Gall Stone
 - b. Morphology of Gall Stone
 - c. Clinical Features and Fate of Gall Stone
 - d. CA Gall Bladder
4. Music Background
5. Participant wide up discussion by picture showing
6. End evaluation feedback collection

(There was one written feedback form describing to expressed Very Happy in above Happy of Mood Meter Bar)

6.f. SGD FP1 Roll No (367-430) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

SGD FP1 PR1 (23.11.2016/ 3:30-4:30PM 45/55 persons)

Topic Discuss - (Cardiovascular System I & II)

Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	27%	29%	38%	0%	7%
After the Class	33%	36%	16%	2%	13%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping (4 Groups)
2. Open book study Group Discussion by Discussion and Presentation Method
3. Group Discussion with pictures & Problems of respective topic
 - a. Rheumatic Cardiac Disease
 - b. Myocardial Infarct
 - c. Aortic Dissection
 - d. Arteriosclerosis
4. Use facilitated teaching style for open discussion and welcome questions.
5. Participant wide up discussion by picture showing
6. End evaluation feedback collection (CVS chapter with 53 pages is so wide for discussion that some of the students get mad & sad on feedback form although most of them are on “Happy Box” after the class.)

7. Report for Third M.B, B.S

7.1 Time Table of Teaching-Learning Activity and its feedback collection for Third M.B, B.S

There are total 7 SGD sessions for Third MB Students on this reporting period (Jul-Dec/2016). I am now submitting the combined feedback report of all these students remaining Roll No (315-375), which have not been conducted as SGD on this period. Since I have conducted the SGD sessions with the total actual attendance of **260** over 358 among total 419 students, I have facilitated SGD with **62.05% of the total Third MB students** who gave me the sandwich feedback in this period. The following table 2 shows in detail in timetable.

Table 4. Time Table of Teaching-Learning Activity and its feedback collection from Third MB (Jul/Dec 2016)

3rd MB Tutorial	A2	PR1	PR2	PR3
RN (106-314) Students Group	RN - 106-166 (Total- 61) 22.9.16/ 11:30AM-12: 30PM Actual Attendance: 51	RN -167-226 (Total – 60) 16.8.16/ 11:30AM-12: 30PM Actual Attendance: 39	RN- 227-270 (Total -44) 6.12.16/ 3:30-4:30PM Actual Attendance: 30	RN - 271-314 (Total – 44) 30.11.2016/12:30-1:30 PM Actual Attendance: 35
RN (1-105/ 315-419) Students Group	RN -1-62 (Total 62) 22.9.16/ 3:30-4:30PM Actual Attendance: 42	RN- 315-375 (Total – 61)	RN - 63-105 (Total – 43) 26.7.16/ 1:30-2:30PM Actual Attendance: 39	RN- 376-419 (Total – 44) 18.10.2016/ 11:30AM-12: 30PM Actual Attendance: 24

7.2 Teaching Learning Practice Overall narrative Report

After making a pilot teaching-learning practice during these 6 months, the following result was undertaken exclusively from Third MB Students. **The lowest score** that they marked as 3.22 over 5 was about the **“Discussion Room is feeling comfortable”** that seems very congested and makes them uncomfortable. I do agree much with that because of many different reasons. PR1 Room has no rotatory exist. And PR2 & PR3 has not given a change to get eye-to-eye contact between students & teacher. Both Final Part 1 & Third MB students give the very low score for the teaching-learning room that we use nowadays.

The second lowest score was **“Questions were encouraged”**. It is not a good result for a teacher dealing with. Although I did not get that score lowest on Final Part I’s feedback, third MB students still assume that they do need to be encouraged for more **“Questions”**. That is the area to be careful & emphasized for next time.

Surprisingly as the same with the final part 1 result, **the third lowest score is length of SGD, which is ever given as just only one hour for a full chapter topic sometimes for a couple chapters.** That ought to be in a more appropriate time for the better teaching learning style.

Others sector is scored as above 3.5/5. The exclusive score for the leading facilitative teacher is getting 4.09/5; the overall practice is scored as 3.5 in average. The following is the detailed data for the feedback.

7.3 SGD Feedback Chart (Third M.B, B.S-Overall)

7.4 SGD Mood Meter Chart (Third M.B, B.S – Overall)

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	25%	29%	34%	7%	5%
After the Class	38%	32%	17%	2%	11%

The above mood meter feedback from the total actual attendance of SGD class, which was total **260 third MB students** shows 38% happy and 32% Ok. Although **70% of the total actual attendance felt great after the SGD classes**, **11% of Third MB Students did not totally agree with the student center teaching-learning practice** because they felt mad after the class by many different reasons shown on respective feedback collected.

The data of feedback form, mood meter and the teaching methods used for each SGD class (7 in total Third MB) are described as No. 7.a to 6.g in the following_

7.a SGD Third MB Roll No (63-105) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

SGD Third MB PR2 (26.7.2016/ 1:30-2:30PM 39/43 persons)

Topic Discuss - (Acute & Chronic Inflammation)

Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	28%	36%	33%	0%	3%
After the Class	23%	64%	5%	3%	5%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. Gallery shows methods
3. Old questions study within grouping
4. Internet browsing
5. Topic discussion on
 - (a. Sequence of events of acute inflammation
 - b. Chronic Granulomatous inflammation)
6. End evaluation feedback collection

7.b SGD Third MB Roll No (167-226) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

SGD Third MB PR2 (16.8.2016/ 11:30AM-12: 30PM 39/60 persons)
Topic Discuss - (Cell Injury & Cell Death, Edema Congestion & Shock)
Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	15%	31%	38%	10%	5%
After the Class	44%	15%	23%	2%	15%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. MSQ/MCQ open book study & Winning prize among the groups
3. Brain Storming by problem Photo questions
 - (a. Thrust Breast or Tiger effect
 - b. Lymphatic edema
 - c. Nutmeg Liver
 - d. Apoptotic body
4. Focus Group Discussion & 2 Minute presentations for the class
5. Googling and Internet browsing
6. End evaluation feedback collection

The very hungry time of the day (11:30-12:30) & many congested topics make them mad after the class.

7.c SGD Third MB Roll No (106-166) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

SGD 3rdMB PR1 (22.9.2016/ 11:30AM-12:30PM 51/61 persons)
Topic Discuss -(Infection of Lympho Reticular, Male & Female Genital, Bone & Joint)
Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	33%	29%	25%	4%	8%
After the Class	33%	27%	16%	4%	20%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. Open book study Group Discussion by World Cafe' Method
3. Group Discussion by World Cafe' Method
 - (a. Chronic Non-Specific Lymph Adenitis
 - b. TB OM
 - c. Pyogenic OM
 - d. Pelvic inflammatory disease)
4. Music Background
5. Facilitator wide up discussion by picture showing
6. End evaluation feedback collection

(Group of feeling mad might be due to **the compact students and hungry lunchtime; as feedback.**)

7.d SGD Third MB Roll No (1-62) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

**SGD 3rdMB PR1 (22.9.2016/ 3:30-4:30PM 42/62 persons)
Topic Discuss -(Infection of Lympho Reticular, Male & Female Genital, Bone & Joint)
Mood Meter feedback**

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	10%	31%	45%	7%	7%
After the Class	50%	33%	14%	0%	2%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. Open book study Group Discussion by World Cafe’ Method
3. Group Discussion by World Cafe’ Method
 - (a. Chronic Non-Specific Lymph Adenitis
 - b. TB OM
 - c. Pyogenic OM
 - d. Pelvic inflammatory disease)
4. Music Background
5. Facilitator wide up discussion by picture showing
6. End evaluation feedback collection (As it was the same topic with morning session, all the methods used were the same but with different feedback result supporting my comments of the morning session)

7.e SGD Third MB Roll No (376-419) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

SGD 3rdMB PR3 RN- 376-419 (18.10.2016/ 11:30AM-12: 30PM 24/44 persons)

Topic Discuss -(Infection of Respiratory Tract Infection)

Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	25%	29%	46%	0%	0%
After the Class	42%	29%	29%	0%	0%

Teaching Learning methods used are

1. Grouping
2. Open book study Group Discussion by World Cafe’ Method
3. Group Discussion by World Cafe’ Method
 - (a. Lobar Pneumonia
 - b. Primary Tuberculosis
 - c. Secondary Tuberculosis)
4. Music Background
5. Participant wide up discussion by picture showing
6. End evaluation feedback collection

(There is one written comment describing, “ Students need to get used to that kind of teaching methods. I like very much your way of teaching learning style. I want all the tutorial sessions to be like this.”)

7.f SGD Third MB Roll No (271-314) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

**SGD 3rdMB PR3 RN- 271-314 (30.11.2016/ 12:30-1:30PM 35/44 persons)
Topic Discuss -(Infections of Liver)
Mood Meter feedback**

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	46%	6%	34%	14%	0%
After the Class	29%	34%	17%	6%	14%

Teaching Learning methods used are

Grouping (4 Groups)

Open book study Group-Discussion and Presentation Method

Group Discussion with Problems of respective topic

- a. Etiology and Pathogenesis of HBV infection
- b. Clinico-Pathologic Syndrome and its clinical presentations
- c. Clinico-Pathologic Syndrome and its morphological changes
- d. Serological markers and its confirmatory investigations of HBV induced hepatitis

Use facilitated teaching style for open discussion and welcome questions.

Participant wide up discussion & student center presentation

End evaluation feedback collection

(Although there is one written comments mentioning the appreciation of that teaching-learning practice, 14% of students after the class had got mad in the mood. That might be due to just after their lunchtime made them inactive.)

7.g SGD Third MB Roll No (227-270) – End Evaluation Feedback/Mood Meter/ Teaching methods used

3rdMB PR2 RN- 227-270 (6.12.2016/ 3:30-4:30PM 30/44 persons)

Topic Discuss -(Tropical & Zoonotic Infections)

Mood Meter feedback

Feeling	Happy	Okay	Neutral	Sad	Mad
Before the Class	20%	43%	17%	10%	10%
After the Class	47%	20%	17%	0%	17%

Teaching Learning methods used are

Grouping (4 Groups)

Open book study Group-Discussion for MCQs & Prize for the winner group

Group Discussion with Problems of respective topic and Presentation Method

- a. Leprosy
- b. Dengue Haemorrhage Fever
- c. Malaria (Etiology & Pathogenesis)
- d. Malaria (Morphological changes & its clinical features)

Use facilitated teaching style for open discussion and welcome questions.

Participant wide up discussion & student center presentation

End evaluation feedback collection. **(Although most of the feedback got great, there were some students who wanted the SGD to be finished very early then they were unhappy after the class because some of them requested me to end it up very early as like other class dismissed early.)**

Comparisom of Feedback Chart between FP 1 (Green) & Third MB (Blue) during Jul-Dec 16

8. Comparison of Feedback Chart between FP1 and Third MB During Jul-Dec 2016

9. Lesson Learnt, Challenges & Solving them

- a) It was very difficult not to get “Sad & Mad” in the mood meter box after the class because of many tight activities in an hour. So **the smarter the preparation is, the more % of the students will be the “Happy” in that box after the class.** Happiness as an indicator in teaching-learning practice poses great challenge to me.
- b) The Internet world makes the students brilliant on surfing the Internet concerning the topic of SGD. If anybody completely omits what they really want to hold their Internet usage, the students will see that teacher as an outsider, which means that the teacher-student relationship will be completely cut off. On the other hand, it is not the very right way that we let them use whatever the social media is in pursuit of silence in the class. So if the teacher really wants to connect with them, they are **allowed to use the Internet in the class** for finding some solutions **while usage of social media & cyber-gaming are strictly banned.** The problem is that the teacher has to approve of and stick to a prescribed reference while they used to admit some undocumented solutions from many Internet sources.
- c) Most students usually sit by their group of colleagues. The SGD class has no discrimination in grouping so then **the students are always mixed up counting** by 1,2,3,4 before any kind of activity so that they have to communicate with new members to get the better communication as well as for group presentation.
- d) Nearly almost all the students have **no practice of self-study before the SGD classes.** It is very difficult to get student-centered discussion in SGD class without **open book study** within very limited one-hour time for the whole chapter. That makes some of the student get mad after the class because some students still prefer passive style teaching-learning practice.
- e) **The early tutorial class (7:30-8:30AM) should be reconsidered** for the effectiveness of teaching learning practice because **most of the students are hungry & sleepy in the SGD class.** They are never active. That was another challenge for the teacher. Although the teacher can teach them with all the traditional teaching (teacher-centered - passive teaching) style, nothing is to point out for hungry & sleepy students for that case. **We should get active and energetic students who are the core values of our university.** Then I let my pocket money out for some sweet candies for the hypoglycemic students of early morning SGD class.
- f) **Not only for the Candy, but also for the teaching aids are all supplied by own budget for the productive SGD class. It is not a very good practice without the budgeting in long term.**

10. Problem Tree Drawing for “Dull & Unhappy Teaching Unit” (Cause → Problem → Effect)

I saw some unhealthy relationship of the student attitude with teaching service provider (mainly teachers). So I let the Final Part I students (Roll No 376-430) discuss the problem tree of “**Dull & Unhappy teaching Unit**” on 16th November 2016. The four FP1 Student groups discuss “the Cause & Effect” as well

as “the Action to be taken” for that problem. **Their constructed feedbacks are now recorded & reported on the ISO document of Pathology Department.** The following topic No.10. is the brief main points to get pointed out.

11. Constructed Feedback & Comprehensive Actions to be carried out for “Dull & Unhappy Teaching Unit”

Table 5 shows the constructed feedback & suggested action plan for “Dull & Unhappy Teaching Unit” exclusively by Final Part I Students

No.	Constructed Feedback	Suggested Action Plan	Remark
1.	<p>Attendance There is no voluntary attendance system for lecture class.</p>	<p>1. The students should not be controlled by Roll call & D-Bar system, which in term is for voluntary attendance.</p>	
2.	<p>Private Study Time There is no private study time for the test and very list of it near the exam.</p>	<p>1. Private study should be vitalized near the tests and exam.</p>	
3.	<p>Teaching Learning Style 1. There is out dated traditional teaching learning practice all the time with the inadequate facilities. 2. We always get the passive learning. 3. Boring and Bad teaching skill of the teachers. 4. Prolonged teaching time with over crowded students. 5. Rare break time</p>	<p>1. The teaching aids & facilities should be upgraded to get a comfortable lecture room. 2. Very mass group teaching and over crowded lecture should be reduced to replace with the assignments & small group teaching. 3. The teaching methods should be changed. 4. Break time during the boring and prolonged teaching time should be provided. 5. Bad & poor traditional teaching style should be changed and updated with attractive ones by the necessary TOT for getting qualified teachers. 6. Early morning lecture time (7:30AM) should be canceled. 7. Teachers should discuss just only short to the points in the class. 8. Students should get a chance to participate actively.</p>	

		<ol style="list-style-type: none">9. No definitive aims make students misunderstood the concept.10. The ratio of students & teachers should be balanced.11. Prize sessions for the outstanding students should be adopted.12. Quiz & Prize Game should be present for the Academic Subjects.13. The students should change their mindset too for the transition of a change.	
4.	The University Campus We do not get the real campus life in the university, which is very bad condition in rainy season.	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The school Wi-Fi should be used with mobile phone.2. The school canteen should be very much cleaned.3. The school should not be drained with rainwater in every case of rain.4. Pigeons and its dirt should be well managed.5. There is no stadium to get a real campus life style.6. The school teaching sessions are so much packed & continuous that there is no time for recreational activities.7. The Entrance of the medical university should not be restricted by the marks of matriculation exam.8. The budget for education should be raised much.	

12. Photo Reporting Sessions

Photo 1. Shows one SGD Group discussing the topic problem

Photo 2. Shows student's presentation on their respective topic problem

Photo 3. Shows student's presentation on their respective topic problem

Photo 4. Shows the hard file feedback documents from total 502 students during Jul-Dec 2016 Reporting Period